

FAIR WORKING GROUP F – THE VALUE OF RESEARCH DATA

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SCHOOL OF CULTURE AND SOCIETY

AARHUS UNIVERSITY

WORKSHOP ON THE VALUE OF DATA
17 JUNE 2024

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WORKING GROUP F – VALUATION OF DATA

Original assignment:

“The working group must prepare proposals for actions that address actions that require special national coordination of the following of the strategy's action areas:

17. What criteria for data value (curation) and economic models do local, national and international data storage services apply to data owners and data controllers in order to assess conservation rationale, economics and sustainability?”

<https://zenodo.org/records/11082776>

WHAT IS VALUE?

- Often expressed in monetary terms
 - Costs to generate data
 - Direct potential to make money
 - “Indirect potential” to stimulate economic growth
- = Applied research
- = Less relevant for fundamental research at universities
- Depends on who you ask!

REFERENCES TO DATA VALUE FROM DIFFERENT VIEWPOINTS

Denmarks Code of Conduct for Research Integrity

“2.2.ii. Researchers are – unless otherwise regulated – responsible for deciding the extent to and duration for which primary material is to be retained. When deciding this, researchers should consider the **value of the primary materials for assessing the results of the research and the physical and technical possibility of storage at the institution.**”

LBK nr 1764 af 26/08/2021: Bekendtgørelse af lov om videreanvendelse af den offentlige sektors informationer.

”§ 11 b. Finansministeren fastsætter nærmere regler om datasæt af **høj værdi, der skal være gratis, maskinlæsbare og tilgængelige via API-grænseflader og i form af massedownloads**, hvis det er relevant.”

Afrapportering - Udvalg om retningslinjer for internationalt forsknings- og innovationssamarbejde (URIS). Maj 2022.

"4.1.1 Kend jeres forsknings værdi og potentiale
Forskningsinstitutioner kan ligge inde med **data, der er unikke og efterspurgt globalt**, eller forskning, der er **tæt på et gennembrud på området**. Det er institutionernes særligt værdifulde forskning, som andre kan have en interesse i at få fat i. Denne forskning bør identificeres og beskyttes.

Data value:

- Potential to support research conclusions
- Costs of storing data
- Something a stakeholder decides
- Accessibility & reusability
- Global demand for data
- Scientific value
- Need to safeguard

THE PLAN

- Summarize current policies for and work with data value in Denmark and abroad
- Not just look at storage providers' perspective, also universities, researchers, etc.
- Develop a framework within which to work with the value of data.
- Test this framework through interviews with stakeholders
- Identify actions that can further the work & recommend specific national initiatives.

FRAMEWORK FOR DATA VALUE

Goal of the framework:

Clarify how the value of research data can be assessed. This framework can be useful for the development of strategies, policies and guidelines governing the management of research data at Danish universities.

First draft of the framework is the result of:

- A workshop in Odense and a workshop in Copenhagen, please some monthly meetings
- UCPHs new data classification model
- *Some* literature (but a thorough literature search still needs to be conducted!)
- A pilot meeting at Rigsarkivet before summer

This is a work in progress, everything we present is open for discussion!

SCOPE FOR THE (FRAME)WORK

We focus on:

1. Research data defined as **digital data** collected, observed, generated, created or reused as part of research activities. This includes digital raw data, computer code, audio and video recordings, digital texts as well as the detailed records of these research outputs.
2. Research data that are part of **research activities at Danish universities**.
3. Value of data in the **context of decision-making in the management of research data**, before, during and after research projects at Danish universities.
4. **Stakeholders** that influence or are **involved in these decisions**.

WHEN ARE ASSESSMENTS OF VALUE IMPORTANT?

VALUE 'TYPES'

1. Cultural / Societal Value

The impact that research data have on our cultural heritage. What is the importance of the research data for our understanding of society now and in the future?

Examples of high value:

- High resolution images of unique physical objects (e.g. paintings)
- Fertilizer seepage data > green transmission
- Danish web data
- Data that archives want to archive

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2. Scientific Value

The contribution that the data make to support or further develop conceptual frameworks within a research discipline. What is the importance of the data in advancing the field of research?

Examples of high value:

- Data underlying the discovery of DNA
- Data that lead to a new method
- Data that funders want to fund
- Data that publishers & peer reviewers want to publish

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3. Market Value

The economic significance of data, e.g. the direct financial gains to the project or organisation or the indirect impact on future value generation in society. Can the data be commercialised by the organisation?

Examples of high value:

- Data underlying an invention to isolate pancreatic progenitor cells
- Data on a method to amplify anthocyanin content in carrots
- Data that big tech, big pharma, weapons industry etc. want to purchase

VALUE 'TYPES'

Examples of high value:

- Data on a rare butterfly species in the Amazonian rainforest
- Data produced in a 25-year-long collaboration between 20 partners across Europe
- Data that cost millions because it relied on very expensive methods
- Data that required ethical approval to be obtained, and it would not be ethically appropriate to repeat the study

2. Scientific Value

The contribution that the data make to support or further develop conceptual frameworks within a research discipline. What is the importance of the data in advancing the field of research?

3. Market Value

The economic significance of data, e.g. the direct financial gains to the project or organisation or the indirect impact on future value generation in society. Can the data be commercialised by the organisation?

4. Replacement value

The resources it requires to (re)create the data. What will it take for the data responsible to regenerate the data? Can data be recreated at all?

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Examples of high value:

- Data on inhabitants' opposition to the regime in North Korea
- Data covered by an NDA with a commercial company
- Health data about children
- Data that lead to severe legal, financial, reputational, ethical consequences when lost.

5. Compliance value

The impact of non-compliance to ethical, legal or contractual obligations. Positively correlated with value. What are the consequences for organisations, human participants, cultural heritage, populations, animals, ecosystems?

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6. ??? value

PREREQUISITES FOR VALUE

Value is hard to obtain, unless:

The data are well-structured

Data are organized in a clear, logical, and systematic manner to facilitate understanding, analysis, and reuse.

The data are well-described

It is clearly documented how the data were obtained and what they represent.

The data are trustworthy and accurate

The data are collected via methods that are quality-controlled, preferably peer-reviewed and assessed to be appropriate to address the research questions.

The data are complete

The data contain all the information that is needed to understand the research and answer the research question.

FACTORS THAT CAN INFLUENCE VALUE

The following factors could have impact on the level of value:

Reach

Data value increases with the number of stakeholders for whom the data has value.

Reusability

Data value increases with the ease of reuse and is there correlated with the “FAIRness” of data.

Timeliness

Data value is influenced by ‘current focus areas’ in society.

Exclusivity

The value of data can be influenced by its abundance when the data are in high-demand.

Innovation

Data value is influenced by the availability of methods to use the data.

DATA VALUE MODEL

THE NEXT STEPS

- Do a larger literature review
- Identify main stakeholders
- Develop interview guide
- Interview main stakeholders, either through 1:1 interviews or focus group interviews
- Interview related initiatives in DK and abroad

Expected output:

- Framework for the value of research data
- Suggestions for follow-up initiatives in DK
- (Checklist or guidance that can help policy development, decision making, etc. in relation to assessing data value throughout the data lifecycle)

ADVICE FROM YOU

- Do you know of any literature on this domain?
- Do you know of any interesting initiatives worldwide?
- Do you have ideas on particular people or organisations to interview?
- Or...could you contribute to an interview or focus group?
- Any other feedback or suggestions?

Thank you!

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